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In this paper, based on a thorough study of relevant scientific literature, the results of the evolution of the introduction and effects of the application of new technologies, i.e. software solutions for enterprise resource planning (ERP - Enterprise Resource Planning), will be presented. Research shows that as one of the key company resources that can provide a competitive advantage in efficiency, companies are increasingly investing in new technologies and artificial intelligence. This is also seen in the growth of the market for comprehensive ERP solutions. The paper will evolve the distribution of market share of global ERP solution suppliers in the world and Europe in 2025. In terms of application possibilities, research shows that companies and organizations are increasingly deciding to implement open source ERP systems and cloud ERP solutions. The use of these systems is already present in the economy of the Republic of Serbia. The purpose of the paper is, among other things, to present the theoretical foundations of ERP systems, present the largest vendors in the world and in Serbia, and assess the current state of ERP system implementation in Serbia. The paper will present the ERP modules that are most often used in 2025. The research will also be based on solving problems that arise during the implementation of ERP system implementation projects. The aim of the paper is to analyze the current state of the ERP market in Serbia in comparison with the state in the world, and highlight their usability in companies, study the advantages and disadvantages and determine the justification for the implementation of open source ERP and cloud ERP. The paper will also present a comparative analysis of global and domestic ERP solutions for 2026. The research will offer answers to questions about the possibilities of using these systems in small and medium-sized enterprises in Serbia and the applicability of ERP systems in business, as well as present the most common pitfalls in the implementation process. This research presents the best ERP software available in 2025, analyzes their key functions and recommends procedures and methodologies for implementation, as well as suggestions for choosing the ERP solution that is most suitable for a specific company and organization.

Keywords: ERP systems, ERP modules, ERP implementation.

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's complex business environment, all organizations are looking for optimal business solutions in order to increase efficiency and competitiveness in relation to the competition. Due to the increasing complexity of business functions and the changing competitive environment, organizations have begun to look for new technologies that would meet their functional needs [2]. In today's business, fast information transfer

and a complete overview of processes are very important with a key note for successful business and management of any company. The literature states that in the modern business environment, digital transformation has become a key factor in the competitiveness and efficiency of companies [18]. The business results of companies in the environment indicate that they are facing increasing pressure to optimize their business processes, reduce costs and improve their response to

market demands. In this context, well-known authors emphasize that the process of digital transformation can bring added value to companies, i.e. higher revenues, competitive advantage, greater success and efficiency [1]. As one of the solutions for the above business situations, the so-called ERP systems appear. Chronologically, comprehensive information solutions began to be developed in the early nineties of the last century. The abbreviation ERP in English stands for Enterprise Resource Planning. These are systems that support all business functions of the company [8]. It can be said that modern ERP systems play an important role in this, enabling standardization, automation and optimization of business processes and ensuring compliance with legal and regulatory requirements [11]. Some authors state that by introducing an ERP system in business, business processes are automated and integrated, which enables data sharing in a single database available in real time [27]. Modern ERP systems include real-time business analytics, cloud deployment, and mobile access to enable seamless collaboration and decision-making across teams. The newspaper is represented by the so-called intelligent ERP systems that, with the help of virtual assistants supported by artificial intelligence, use business data to predict market trends and help improve business processes. Microsoft 365 Copilot appears as one of the better-known virtual assistants, which helps with everyday tasks. In addition, these systems are designed for process automation, which reduces the workload of employees and increases their efficiency [7]. Practice shows that the digital transformation of the company leads to a smart organization where we are talking about the automation of the data

storage process, innovation and optimal user experience. Well-known authors state that these processes take place with the help of new technologies, such as artificial intelligence (English Artificial Intelligence - AI), machine learning (English Machine Learning - ML), Internet of Things (English Internet of Things - IoT) and analytics [13]. Other authors emphasize that efforts aimed at introducing artificial intelligence and cyber security into ERP systems and ERP systems in the cloud require large initial investments in software and hardware, hiring experts and training employees [26]. The literature states that ERP provides mechanisms for information exchange within an organization, as it enables precise and up-to-date access to information, faster transaction processing and high data quality. However, during the implementation project, both great opportunities and great risks arise [16].

2. THEORETICAL BASICS OF ERP SYSTEMS

ERP systems include and control all business areas, in support of this, the data show that 92% of highly successful small and medium-sized enterprises currently use or plan to use ERP systems [9]. Below, Figure 1 shows the most commonly used modules that are included in ERP systems: finance module, procurement module, production module, human resources management module, supply chain management (SCM) module, inventory management module, project management module, client relationship management module, risk management module and marketing automation module [12]. The following Figure 1 presents the 11 top ERP modules in 2025:

Fig. 1. ERP modules [24].

Realization of the project of introducing the ERP business information system, as one of the key resources, is always a complex and expensive project with far-reaching consequences for the organization. Well-known authors state that ERP systems, among other things, are implemented in companies with the aim of improving data quality, optimizing data transmission and increasing the ability to analyze data. The same authors point out that they enable the collection and analysis of data from different areas of business through a centralized database [5]. ERP solutions can be divided into depending on the method of installation [25]:

1. Cloud-based ERP solutions, running on remote servers maintained by software vendors and accessible via the Internet. The advantage of such solutions is that they eliminate the need for high initial investments in

hardware, which is especially suitable for companies with limited IT resources. In this model, companies access the ERP solution through a subscription model, and the software is installed on the external servers of the solution provider [15].

2. On-site ERP solutions, which run on the organization's own servers. This approach allows for complete control over the data and the system, but requires a larger financial investment in infrastructure and maintenance.

3. Implementing a hybrid ERP solution combines elements of on-premises and cloud solutions. This attempts to leverage the benefits of both, allowing organizations to store their sensitive data on local servers and use the cloud for scalable and collaborative functions

3. ERP SOLUTION IMPLEMENTATION PARADIGMS

The introduction of an ERP system, in addition to its numerous advantages, also brings a number of disadvantages that companies must take into account. However, no matter how much the project is implemented, and this is done periodically in almost all organizations, it is often the case that the project ends unsuccessfully, mainly due to ignorance and failure to comply with the rules for managing such projects. Some data show that 40% of all ERP installations achieve only partial implementation, while 20% of ERP implementation attempts prove to be a complete failure. The percentage of failure in the introduction of ERP systems is a figure that affects the lower use of these systems in SMEs, because unsuccessful implementation brings high costs [10]. Other research indicates that the failure rate of ERP systems can be even higher than 50%. These failures are mainly due to the lack and inadequacy of the special prerequisites required for the successful implementation of ERP [16]. Research in practice shows that investment in a business information system represents a significant item in the organization's costs and should be budgeted for. In addition to the financial moment, the time and effort that management and employees invest during the implementation of the project are significant. Especially in organizations that already have negative experiences with previous similar projects, employees will be reluctant to start implementation at all if all the conditions are not provided for the entire project to be implemented to the end. Also, what is rarely considered is the price, or lost profits if the organization does not introduce a new system. The longer the organization postpones the purchase and introduction of a modern business system, the longer it will delay its presence on the global market, and will not realize the benefits and savings that the new system brings or achieve a comparative advantage over the competition. In this regard, we must pay attention to the fact that the Information System is part of the infrastructure of a company or organization, which is why it is strategically important for the survival and success of the company [30]. Then, the

ERP solution and the company's information system are introduced with the task of increasing productivity, not vice versa. Learning from mistakes and successes is no less important. A series of questions and answers arise when we decide to purchase a new business system to support the work of our company or organization. In the process of accepting such a business risk, managers are asked questions that many do not know how to answer for the simple reason that it is not their area. It often happens that when deciding what to buy and which offer is the best, decisions are made quickly, which is why decisions are made that do not rely on professional knowledge. Most often, the price is the only element that decides on the software supplier, which is fundamentally the wrong basis. That is why the question arises of which ERP solution to buy, whether they are domestic solutions, or are better foreign solutions, the offer of which is very large today. Company management and decision-making staff are in most cases not familiar with what an ERP solution is, what vertical solutions are and what their task is.

4. ERP SOLUTION SELECTION PROCESS

Before purchasing any ERP solution, it is necessary to define well the business processes, the organization and determine the internal team, composed of the main managers of the company who have a vision and want to introduce ERP. After defining the needs, the choice of solutions should be started. Only after that can the right selection of an ERP solution be made, as it is possible to create evaluation metrics. A good ERP must be applicable in different areas of business and therefore should have tools for adapting to the information requirements of users. There are thousands of different providers of ERP solutions on the market, but only a small number of them manage to fight the competition and achieve a significant market share. In this regard, the data shows that the size of the European ERP market in 2025 is 12.67 billion dollars, which represents 22.7% of the global market. The following Figure 2 shows the share of the largest vendors of ERP systems in Europe.

Fig. 2: Market share distribution of global ERP solution providers in Europe 2025 [21].

It is important to emphasize that global ERP solutions are mainly designed for multinational companies. The global ERP market size is estimated at 73 billion dollars in 2025, while the estimated ERP market size for 2026 is 81 billion dollars, which represents an increase of 11% compared to 2025. The global providers on the market for larger companies and organizations are: SAP S/4HANA, Oracle EBS, Microsoft Dynamics 365, IFS, Infor Inc. While for companies up to 1000

employees, the global providers are: Microsoft Dynamics 365 Business Central (BC), SAP Business One, NetSuite, Sage X3, Infor, Odoo. For small businesses, we have the following providers: Workday, Work (etc) and Syspro. Datalab (PANTHEON), SAOP (iCenter, mini-MAX), MIT Informatika (Orkester) and Birokrat IT (Birokrat). Research in practice shows that the five largest global providers include: SAP with a 25.8%

share of the total global market for such systems, followed by Oracle with a 19.8% share, followed by Microsoft with 18.4%, IFS with 9.2%, Infor with 8.5%, etc. In this context, SAP is known for its comprehensive ERP platform and high degree of adaptability. SAP's ERP revenues in 2024 were \$8.6 billion. In this regard, as many as 98 of the world's 100 largest companies use their solutions, while 85 of the world's 100 largest companies use SAP S/4HANA, which, with its advanced technology and real-time data processing capabilities, enables companies to effectively implement digital transformation and improve their business efficiency. The global company SAP is an international giant in the field of business applications and application software for enterprises. Approximately 80% of SAP users are small and medium-sized enterprises [25]. The fact that SAP is probably the best solution, but how the project is introduced, i.e. how the system is implemented, is much more important. It often happens that a quality implementation of a more modest ERP solution turns out to be of higher quality than an amateurishly implemented SAP. It is important to know that software alone is not enough to have ERP in a company, it is only one of the prerequisites.

Then comes Oracle, which stands out with a strong portfolio of applications and services, as well as a focus on business analytics. Oracle is the largest ERP vendor

by revenue with \$8.7 billion in 2024. Essentially, the Oracle Unified Method (OUM) is a working methodology based on Oracle standards and allows covering the entire project life cycle. OUM provides an implementation scope that is fast, scalable and business-oriented. It also contains a comprehensive project management framework. OUM has a structured but flexible scope. Its defined operational framework helps in anticipating the needs and critical dependencies of the project, as well as in measuring business results [19].

The next provider is Microsoft, which stands out for its easy integration with other tools and ease of use. Microsoft's ERP revenues in 2024 were \$5.4 billion, making it the third largest ERP vendor. Microsoft's methodology for faster, optimized and more efficient implementation of an information system is called Microsoft Sure Step, abbreviated as MDSS. It can be used when implementing any Microsoft Dynamics solution (Dynamics 365 Business Central, Dynamics 365 Sales, as well as other Dynamics solutions).

And finally, Infor, which is known for its specialized solutions for certain industries, Infor's ERP revenues in 2024 were \$3.0 billion, making it the sixth largest ERP vendor by revenue, while Sage stands out for its solutions intended for small and medium-sized enterprises [6]. The following table 1 presents a comparison of the world's leading ERP solutions.

Criteria	SAP S/4HANA	Oracle NetSuite	Microsoft Dynamics 365	Odoo (Enterprise)
Mobile Application	SAP Mobile Start (high security)	NetSuite Mobile (complete ERP on the phone)	Dynamics 365 App (dedicated for Sales/CRM)	Odoo Mobile (dedicated desktop version)
Starting Price (approx.)	From ~\$180 per user/month	From ~\$99 per user/month + base fee	\$70-\$180 per user/month (depending on module)	From ~\$25 per user/month (Standard Plan)
Hidden Costs	High implementation and consulting costs	Annual renewals of licenses and modules	Additional Azure services and data storage costs	Hosting (if not on Odoo Online) and customizations
Offline Work	Limited (depends on module)	None (exclusive Cloud)	Available for field services and sales	Available for POS (sales locations)
Implementation Time	12+ months	3-6 months	4-9 months	1-4 months

Table 1. Comparison of the world's leading ERP solutions for 2026.

Choosing the best ERP software solution for your organization is not a one-size-fits-all decision. In terms of functionality, small and medium-sized businesses can benefit from the affordability and modularity of solutions like Odoo, Zoho, or Acumatica, while large corporations may prefer the depth and complexity of platforms like SAP S/4HANA, Oracle NetSuite, or Microsoft Dynamics 365. SAP S/4HANA is often considered the gold standard of ERP software for large enterprises. Oracle NetSuite, a long-standing leader in the ERP market, offers a complete ERP software solution in the cloud that suits businesses of all sizes, especially mid-sized companies and large enterprises. Microsoft Dynamics 365 offers a comprehensive and highly customizable solution that combines ERP and CRM functionality in a single integrated platform. Built on the Microsoft Azure cloud infrastructure, Dynamics 365 enables native integration with Microsoft 365 tools like Teams, Excel, and Power BI. Odoo stands out as one of the most versatile and cost-effective ERP solutions for small and medium-sized businesses. Its open-

source basis allows for great adaptability, which makes it particularly attractive for developers and companies with specific business processes. Regarding the Serbian market, interest in existing ERP solutions for a customer relationship support module or the so-called CRM module has recently increased. Other opportunities that are emerging for Serbian ERP solution providers are also related to globalization or the offer of products on the market of former groups of countries. Manufacturers in the production of ERP solutions are expanding. When it comes to regional ERP software, the most common solution in our region is the Slovenian Pantheon solution, from the Datalab company, which has based its business on a widely branched partner network and offers multiple connected systems. While the largest domestic regional player is the Novi Sad-based company M&I System. This is precisely how opportunities arise for connecting our and foreign companies, without excluding the possibility of participating in other world markets.

CRITERIA	GLOBAL (SAP, DYNAMICS)	LOCAL (PANTHEON, BIZNISOFT)	OPEN SOURCE (ODOO)
LEGAL COMPLIANCE	Through local partners	Proven and reliable	Through community/partners
E-INVOICING (SEF)	Integration via connectors	Direct integration	Via modules from local companies
IMPLEMENTATION COST	High (€10,000 - €100,000+)	Affordable (€1,000 - €10,000)	Medium (depends on scope)
SUPPORT	Certified partners	Local teams (in Serbian)	Local IT partners
SCALABILITY	Practically unlimited	Medium to high	High

Table 2. Comparison of domestic ERP solutions for 2026.

Practical results show that the costs of implementing an ERP solution do not only include the introduction of the ERP system, but also its functioning and maintenance. The literature states that the maintenance of an ERP system in a company is considered any change to the software once it is already running. We distinguish between corrective and adaptive maintenance, as well as product care [4]. For the reasons stated above, the introduction of an ERP system is a large project that can be mastered step by step. With precise definition of business problems, critical assessment of the supplier, software solution and implementation methodology, active involvement in the project and the implementation process, and strict implementation within the set plan, we can easily ensure that costs and risks are reduced to the minimum possible extent and at the same time increase the chances of successful implementation of the ERP solution. The success of the solution implementation is not guaranteed. Data shows that in 2025, as many as 72% of companies had problems with digital transformation. In this context, implementers must openly communicate with solution users and provide them with comprehensive training, which can significantly contribute to greater acceptance of changes and reduction of resistance. The most common problem in implementation is the lack of knowledge, or adequate staff (44%), followed by the lack of financial resources (41%), while 33% of companies stated that the reason was that the business cannot be adapted to changes in the environment. There are also still misconceptions among business people, which is confirmed by the data that as many as half of companies believe that digital transformation is not necessary for successful business. Statistical data also showed that ERP is used by 35% of companies, of which 34% are small, 61% are medium-sized and 92% are large companies. In order for the choice of solution and supplier to be as successful as possible, this process needs to be approached systematically, step by step [20]. The steps are as follows:

- defining business needs,
- involving key stakeholders,
- defining the budget,
- analyzing the market offer,
- assessing functionality and adaptability,
- the possibility of localization,
- assessing the user experience,
- checking integration,

- assessing suppliers,

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

When writing the paper, the methods of compilation, description and comparative method were used, which helps us in describing concepts and reviewing the literature. The latest professional literature and research were studied, mainly from foreign sources. In addition to the above, the survey method was also used, which brings us the desired answers and data necessary for the research. The survey results were analyzed using the method of business analysis of survey results. The final research results were shown and presented by synthesizing the findings of business analysis and implementation.

5. RESULTS

The results indicate that technological progress, especially in the field of information technology, accelerated business changes, triggering the transformation of traditional business models. In this context, at the center of this transformation are ERP systems - modern tools for planning and resource management, which have become an indispensable part of business practice today. The results show that ERP solutions can be adapted to businesses of all sizes and industries, offering flexibility, scalability and efficiency. The most represented is Cloud ERP, which makes up 70% of the market and is growing at a rate of 14.5% per year compared to 2% growth of on-premise solutions. The size of the cloud ERP market in 2025 is \$51 billion, representing 70% of the total ERP market. In terms of functionality, while locally installed ERP systems allow a greater level of control over the business, cloud ERP systems are more financially affordable for businesses of all sizes. It is for these reasons that there is a growing shift towards ERP solutions in the cloud, which has grown significantly since 2016 and is still growing. A study by Gartner estimates that 53% of all ERPs were installed in the cloud in 2021 (Schwarz, 2022). The results of a review of relevant research indicate that with rapid technological advances and the digitalization of business, ERP solutions have developed to the point where they have become accessible to both small and medium-sized and large companies [3].

5.DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Based on the research results, we can conclude that the successful implementation of an ERP system does not only depend on technical implementation, but

equally, if not more, on careful planning, realistic expectations and, above all, a focus on the human aspect. At the same time, the development of ERP solutions has begun to be marked by current technological trends such as artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML), the Internet of Things (IoT) and data analytics. By incorporating these technological capabilities, ERP solutions enable improved automation, business trend prediction and improved interactive data analysis [17]. This research confirmed that organizational factors and employee workload management are key to achieving not only project goals, but also long-term user satisfaction and efficiency, which is the foundation of successful digital transformation. In implementation projects, successful human capital management in such projects is not only crucial for the well-being of employees, but also directly affects the achievement of set business goals and the profitability of the entire investment in a new information system. Well-known authors indicate that the point of profitability (return on investment, ROI) increases only after a certain period, when users learn to properly use the capabilities of the implemented solution [14].

6. CONCLUSIONS

Modern companies and enterprises are constantly striving to increase efficiency and improve their own processes. They can do this using a number of different systems that provide automation, fast information flow and comprehensive monitoring of what is happening in all departments of the company. In this sense, ERP systems, or comprehensive software solutions, play a role, which represent the backbone of modern information systems in developed companies, because they enable fast and efficient transfer of information within the company. Essentially, with ERP you have one application where you can see: how much goods you have in stock, which orders are waiting, how much you have invoiced this month, which employees have days off, and how much it costs you to produce one product. In terms of implementation, it is important to emphasize that before each implementation, it is necessary to study the company or the entire supply chain into which the ERP system is being introduced. Only after determining the needs can a specific ERP system be truly recommended for a particular organization or company. For the above reasons, ERP systems are increasingly being applied and are becoming the subject of research, in this sense, based on the data obtained, we believe that similar research in the coming years could help to better understand the development and usability of these systems. We also believe that in the coming years it would be useful to repeat the research on the usability of ERP systems in the Republic of Serbia and the surrounding area. The results show that ERP is not only for large corporations, in 2026 there are solutions that are accessible to companies with 5-10 employees. The key is to follow the prescribed methodology, i.e. the correct selection and phased implementation. As for the perspective, future projects should start with better organization and planning, where it is crucial to set a realistic timeframe with the involvement of operational users, formally allocate time for work on the project and ensure the replacement of regular tasks for the most stressful team members. In the coming years, we expect

that the research will develop in the direction of increasing the product offer to clients in the form of so-called foreign execution or so-called "outsourcing". Based on the research findings, the above-mentioned recommendations for optimizing the management and implementation of future projects for the implementation of complex business information systems have been formulated.

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